

THE TEACHER-DISCIPLE TRADITION CONTINUES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11399162>

Abstract: This article provides information about teachers and students of Professor Rozibi Khodzhaeva. The teacher-apprentice tradition in teaching the Dutor instrument is unique

Key words: Music education, folklore, education system, musical instrument performance, art, Rubob.

Introduction:

Uzbek music performance has been passing from mouth to mouth, from teacher to student for many years, developing and passing from ancestors to generations. At the same time, Uzbek musical instruments have been passed from hand to hand for centuries and years, developed, improved and perfected for many years. Our musical instruments are among the oldest and most diverse instruments in the world. Among the Uzbek folk instruments, the traditional forms of dutor, tanbur, qabuz, gijjak, doyra and rubob instruments have been passed from hand to hand for many years and have reached us and were performed by our ancestors who lived in ancient times and passed on to the next generations. We can learn about musical instruments and famous musicians of the past from miniatures created in the 15th-16th centuries, cultural monuments found as a result of archaeological excavations, various pictures carved on the walls of buildings and copper vessels.

Since our musical instruments have come down to us from ancient times, it means that our instruments were preserved by the musicians who lived in ancient times and came down to us. Musicians learned to play these instruments from their teachers, and we can tell that there was a tradition of master-disciple from that time. Even today, if we want to learn to play an instrument, we definitely need a teacher. We learn to play any musical instrument and achieve creative achievements thanks to the passion and thorough knowledge of our teachers. There is a saying in our people that the teacher is as great as your father. Indeed, our teachers are as great as our fathers and as kind as our mothers, and they have been giving us their knowledge.

Speaking of teachers, here we would like to talk about our teacher Rozibi Madievna Khodjaeva, winner of the "For Loyal Services" medal, professor of the Uzbekistan State Conservatory.

Rozibi Khodjaeva was born on March 25, 1959 in the village of Krasnogorsk, Tashkent region. Rozibi, who saw her brother playing the rubab, also became more interested in music. When his brother Ma'murjon started studying at the boarding school of the Republican Music School named after R. Glier, Rozibi also started going to the music school to study in the rubab class. Later, with the advice of his brother Ma'murjon, he continues to study in the class of dutor instrument from rubab instrument, and in

1974, after completing the 8th grade of the secondary school and the 5th grade of the music school, he entered the Hamza music school in Tashkent. Speaking about our teacher Rozibi Khodjaeva, we would like to talk about their teachers.

At Rozibi Khodzhaeva Khamza School of Music, they learn the dutor instrument in the classes of our demanding, strict, beloved teacher Sotvoldi Karimov. Teacher Sotvoldi Karimov was very demanding and strict. The teacher has always been under the control of the students, starting with their hairstyle, dressing, cleanliness, orderly completion of classes, and how to behave in public places. Having studied under such a demanding teacher, Rozibi graduated with excellent grades and entered the Tashkent State Conservatory. He also studies at the conservatory under the demanding teacher Feoktist Nikiforovich Vasiliev. He learns from his teacher how to make a clean sound on the dutor instrument, how to get a clear sound when the fingers are placed on the frets, how to place the fingers on the frets in a row, that is, how to artistically reveal the appliqué and the piece being played.

Rozibi Khodzhaeva, who was such a demanding, strict, educated, and at the same time learned from teachers who were as kind as her father, has been teaching her students the knowledge she received from her teachers to this day.

If we count the number of students trained by teacher Rozibi Khodjaeva, we may not be able to count them accurately. We must mention that there are many students of them in different regions of our Republic, and these students, in turn, train their students and come to the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan as "grandchildren" to study in Rozibi Khodjaeva's classes. At the same time, the school of Professor Rozibi Khodzhaeva was created, developed and continues at the Conservatory. Rozibi Khodjaeva's students are not only in Uzbekistan, but also in America, France, and Japan. Several of her students are making the Uzbek musical instrument dutor soz popular abroad, and are preparing students by teaching them the knowledge they received from Rozibi Khodjaeva.

Including, 3 students of Rozibi Khodjaeva, 1 "granddaughter" students of Uzbekistan State Conservatory are teaching their students the knowledge they got from their teacher. These are senior teachers Durдона Haydaralieva and Malohat Nabieva, teacher Khurshida Mirsolikhova and "granddaughter" student Sarvinoz Israilova. They have been learning from Rozibi Khodzhaeva the secrets of the correct sitting position on the dutor instrument, placing the fingers of the left hand in a row on the dutor frets, and how to have a pure sound on the dutor instrument, and have been teaching them to their students. We did not talk about the fact that our musical instruments passed from hand to hand over the years, developed and polished, and reached us. In fact, Rozibi Khodzhaeva's knowledge acquired at the music school was developed and polished under the guidance of teacher Sotvoldi Karimov, and under the guidance of F.N. Vasilev, she was brought into a clear order. The developed, polished knowledge received from such teachers was passed on from the teacher, Professor Rozibi Khodjaeva to the senior teacher Durдона Haydaralieva, and then it was passed on by other students to their grandchildren and great-grandchildren according to the tradition of mentor-disciple, and it has developed and reached today's young generation.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, we can say that as long as there is a tradition of imparting knowledge from the teacher to the student, the teacher-student tradition will continue for many years in our country and such a tradition will never disappear or stop.

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